

Recommended agronomic practices for growing rice and wheat in alkali soil were followed.

The results indicate that grasses grown for 2 yr sufficiently ameliorated the soil for a successful rice-wheat sequence. Rice yields in plots without amendment were possible the third year, and wheat yields the fourth year. Yields of rice and wheat in plots where 12.5 t gypsum/ha was applied and where karnal grass was grown for 2 yr did not differ significantly.

Changes of soil pH as a result of the treatments are shown in the figure. The pH reduction was greatest in plots

Rice - wheat yields in alkali soil treated with gypsum or grass crops. Haryana, India, 1979-84.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)									
	1979-80		1980-81		1981-82		1982-83		1983-84	
	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat	Rice	Wheat
No amendment	0	0	1.0	0	4.6	0.6	5.7	2.7	5.1	3.8
Gypsum	3.7	2.6	4.5	1.3	5.8	3.4	6.5	3.6	4.8	4.6
P 1 yr	—	—	3.8	0.1	5.8	1.6	6.8	3.3	5.4	4.7
P 2 yr	—	—	—	—	5.3	2.6	5.9	3.4	5.1	4.9
P 3 yr	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.6	3.0	5.9	4.3
K 1 yr	—	—	4.1	0.3	5.4	2.1	6.6	3.6	5.4	4.6
K 2 yr	—	—	—	—	6.1	3.4	5.8	3.8	5.2	5.2
K 3 yr	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.8	3.2	5.5	4.1
CD (0.05)	—	—	—	—	—	—	ns	0.5	0.5	0.6

^aP = para grass, K = karnal grass.

where gypsum was applied. For the grasses, pH reduction was greater in

plots where karnal grass was grown for 2 yr. □

Effect of pyrite and fertilizer on rice protein quality

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Protein concentration in grain increases with high fertility. Because the poor biological value of rice protein is

attributed to the deficiency of essential amino acids, such as lysine and tryptophan, we studied the effect of different levels of pyrite and fertilizer on protein quality of rice.

The soil was slightly saline-alkali with moderate pH and exchangeable sodium percentage. Pyrite was applied 10 d before transplanting Saket 4 to ensure complete oxidation in the experimental field. N as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash were applied.

Half the N and all the P and potash were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied 30 d after transplanting.

Grain samples were harvested with a sickle and dried in an oven at 60 °C. The samples were hand pounded to brown rice, ground to powder, and passed through a 60-mesh sieve for chemical analysis. N content in the defatted samples was determined by microKjeldahl method; that value was

multiplied by a factor of 5.95 to get protein content. Protein fractions were estimated on the basis of solubility in water (albumin), sodium chloride (globulin), ethyl alcohol (prolamin), and sodium hydroxide (glutelin). Lysine content was measured using trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid reagent. Protein fractions and lysine content were calculated as percent of grain.

Protein content increased in all treatments. The highest protein content was obtained with 600 kg pyrite/ha and 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha.

Fractionation revealed that the major

Effect of pyrite and fertilizers on brown rice protein quality. Faizabad, India, 1985–86 kharif.

Character (%)	Range	Mean	CD at 5%	Character	Coefficient of correlation ^a
Protein	8.00–9.00	8.58	0.40	Protein vs albumin	-0.46
Albumin	0.53–0.74	0.62	0.07	Protein vs globulin	-0.32
Globulin	0.55–0.77	0.69	0.09	Protein vs prolamin	0.55*
Prolamin	0.32–0.65	0.51	0.14	Protein vs glutelin	0.76**
Glutelin	6.09–7.13	6.65	0.50	Prolamin vs glutelin	0.65**
Lysine	0.22–0.30	0.26	0.04	Protein vs lysine	-0.81**

^a * = significant at 5%, ** = significant at 1%.

amount of protein was in the form of glutelin (6.65%) (see table). Higher fertility slightly increased the prolamin and glutelin fractions. Lysine content

decreased with increased pyrite and NPK. Protein content was positively correlated with prolamin and glutelin and negatively correlated with lysine. □

Response to nitrogen of rice in sodic soil

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We studied the influence of N level (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha) on yield in highly barren sodic soil without amendment. Soil was sandy loam with pH 10.3, 90% exchangeable sodium, 0.35 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g, 30 kg available N/ha, 21 ppm Olsen's

extractable P, and adequate available K in the 0–15 cm layer.

Damoder (CSR-1) variety was transplanted 16 Jul 1981 and 1982. Zinc sulfate at 5.5 kg/ha with one-third N as urea was applied at transplanting, with 1/3 N at 25 and 1/3 N at 50 d after transplanting. The crop was harvested 17 Nov 1981 and 16 Nov 1982.

Grain and straw yields increased significantly with N level (Table 1). The N content of grain and straw also increased (Table 2). □

Table 2. N content in grain and straw by N level. Karnal, India, 1981–82.

N level (kg/ha)	N content (%)			
	1981		1982	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
0	1.08	0.28	1.00	0.33
60	1.22	0.30	1.04	0.44
120	1.33	0.33	1.13	0.47
180	1.44	0.35	1.30	0.53
CD (0.05)	0.10	0.04	0.08	0.05

Table 1. Effect of N level on yield and yield attributes. Karnal, India, 1981–82.

N level (kg/ha)	1981				1982				pH at 0–15 cm after harvest in 1982		
	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)		Yield (t/ha)	
				Grain	Straw					Grain	Straw
0	83.4	7.8	14.4	1.3	2.4	98.7	6.1	14.9	1.4	2.3	9.8
60	95.1	11.5	15.6	2.2	3.7	113.0	10.9	17.3	2.5	4.2	9.8
120	105.5	13.1	16.4	2.9	4.9	117.9	12.5	17.7	3.0	5.3	9.7
180	111.0	14.5	17.0	3.6	5.9	124.8	13.8	18.5	3.4	5.9	9.7
CD (0.05)	6.5	0.9	0.8	0.4	0.6	7.2	1.1	0.7	0.4	0.6	–

Comparative efficiency of puddling implements

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We evaluated the performance of different puddling implements — rotary power tiller, iron puddler, iron plow,

country wooden plow, and wooden puddler — during the 1982–84 monsoon seasons and their effect on yield in newly terraced land.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with five replications. All implements except the rotary power tiller were bullock drawn. The plots were puddled with two criss-cross passes except with the country wooden plow, which had the farmer practice of four

passes. Plot size was 9.6 × 4.2 m. Soil was clay loam, lateritic with pH 5.6 and 1.19% organic C.

After puddling, Jaya was transplanted in early Jul at 20 × 15-cm spacing. The crop was fertilized with 100–22–41 kg NPK/ha. All the P and K and 40% N were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation.

In 1983, yield was significantly